

SYNTHESIS OF PHARMACOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES BASED ON THE COORDINATION COMPOUND OF NICKEL (II) WITH GLUTARIC ACID AND NICOTINAMIDE

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Relevance. In the 20th century, it was found that the pancreas is very rich in nickel. Nickel is one of the trace elements necessary for the normal development of the human body. Experimental studies on living organisms have shown that nickel deficiency leads to a sharp delay in growth and development, anemia due to a decrease in the level of hemoglobin in the blood. Nickel enhances the antidiuretic effect of the pituitary gland. Nickel actively promotes the metabolism of vitamins. The element regulates the flow and absorption of calcium in the body. However, inorganic metal salts are toxic, so much attention is paid to coordination compounds of metals with bioligands, since the bound metal has less toxicity and greater biological activity.

Methods and techniques. When performing this study, nickel nitrate salt and analytical grade caustic soda were used. Ligands glutaric acid (GLA) and nicotinamide (ANC) of the pharmacopoeial grade. The individuality of the isolated complex was studied by comparing the X-ray diffraction patterns of the starting substance and the complex compound, which were obtained on an XRD-6100 powder diffractometer. Thermal analysis of the complex was carried out on a NETZSCH STA-409 PG thermal analyzer in the temperature range of 400°C. Quantitative determination of the metal was carried out in an atomic adsorption spectrophotometer AA-7000 (Shimadzu, Japan). Nitrogen was determined by the Dumas micromethod, and water content was determined gravimetrically. IR spectra were recorded on a Cary 630 Fourier transform IR spectrophotometer in the range 400-4000 cm⁻¹ (Ftir Agilent Technologies, USA) complete with a MIRacle-10 attenuated total internal reflection (ATR) attachment with a diamond/ZnSe prism (spectral range on the wavenumber scale - 4000÷400 cm⁻¹; resolution - 4 cm⁻¹, sensitivity signal-to-noise ratio - 60,000:1; scanning speed - 20 spectra per second).

Purpose of the study. Based on the above, a targeted synthesis and study of the physicochemical properties of a mixed-ligand coordination compound Ni (II) with bioligands - glutaric acid and nicotinamide - was carried out.

Results. The synthesis of the complex compound Ni(GLA-2H)(ANK)₂·H₂O (where the sign “-H” denotes the deprotonated ligand) was carried out as follows: 0.004 mol of glutaric acid was dissolved in 5 ml of an aqueous solution containing 0.008 mol of sodium hydroxide. A solution of 0.004 mol of metal nitrate salt in 5 ml of water was added to it. The resulting clear solution was added with stirring to 50 ml of an ethanol solution of 0.008 mol of nicotinamide. The mixture was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 2 days. The precipitate that formed was separated and washed with ether.

Conclusions. Based on the above, we can conclude that in the synthesized mixed-ligand complex compound of the composition Ni(GLA-2H)(ANK)₂·H₂O, deprotonated glutaric acid exhibits tetradentate behavior and is coordinated to the metal through the oxygen atoms of

the carboxylate group, and nicotinamide is monodentate with the participation of the carbonyl oxygen atom. Water molecule in the $\text{Ni}(\text{GLA}-2\text{H})(\text{ANK})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ outer-sphere complex. Such coordination of ligands probably occurs in the polymeric structure of the complexes. Thus, it has been established that the new nickel coordination compound being studied is two times less toxic than nickel nitrate salt.

Literature

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